

THE SYSTEM OF HUMANIZATION OF TEACHER AND STUDENT RELATIONS IN
THE CONTENT OF THE DIDACTIC SYSTEM.

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Abstract: Currently, we can emphasize the special relevance of pedagogical research; in the field of humanization of education in general and humanization of didactic relations between teachers and students in particular. In this article, brief information about the development of the system of humanizing the relationship between the teacher and the student in the content of the didactic system will be given.

Key words: Didactics, Didactic system, Educational process and its task, principle of humanization, education, future teacher.

Main part: Didactics is a branch of pedagogy. He is engaged in the theory of education. The term "didactics" was first used in Europe in the 17th century by scientists who wrote about the teaching and learning process. The Czech pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius developed the didactic aspects of educating and educating children and adolescents in his Great Didactic (1657). The German pedagogue Adolph Diesterweg in his work "Instructions for the training of German teachers" (1834-35) emphasized that didactics is a separate part of pedagogy that describes the theory of education. After that, the view of didactics as a science of educational theory became widespread. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, special monographs on didactics began to be created.

In modern pedagogy, didactics is considered as a separate field dealing with the theory of education and enlightenment. Determining the content of education, discovering the laws of the educational process, and finding the most effective methods and ways of teaching are the main problems of didactics. The philosophical-theoretical basis has a great role in determining the essence and direction of didactics. For a long time, in many communist countries, Marxism-Leninism was considered as a methodological basis that determines the direction of development of didactics. But when it became known that the scientific basis of this doctrine is empty, it is a biased (tendential) view that is deprived of the opportunity to correctly and objectively show the laws of the development of society and nature, and it became impossible to rely on it. Later, in many Muslim countries, the philosophy of speech is considered as the methodological basis of national didactics. Because it was realized that aspects such as the creation of the universe, the laws of development, human cognitive abilities, the role of enlightenment in personal development and self-awareness can be explained in a comprehensible way only by relying on this philosophical basis. Kalam's philosophy is notable for showing that education is a means of knowing the world, that there is no end to the process of knowing, but the knowledge that a person can know is limited.

Relevance and statement of the research problem. A change in the pedagogical paradigm led to a radically different perspective. considering the main didactic relations not as an activity, but as an interaction of individuals" requires a different understanding of the science of pedagogy as a pedagogy of creativity, a pedagogy of humanizing the school, different from the traditional

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one. this is the principle of developing the creative personality of a growing person and the principle of the eye - the principle of humanization of education. Need

Currently, we can emphasize the special relevance of pedagogical research; in the field of humanization of education in general and humanization of didactic relations between teachers and students in particular.

First, human interdependence in an increasingly complex high-tech civilization makes clear "human problems" relevant.

Secondly, the future demands more and more that educational processes are primarily focused on the "inner life" of students, its orientation to values*, self-esteem and feelings. . The only type of education that can achieve such goals as the maintenance of psychological health of young people, a sense of civic responsibility and the formation of a decent moral consciousness is education that takes into account the main important thing, the importance of the "subjective factor" in learning.

As you can see, the roots of the problem of humanizing the relationship between the teacher and the student, the humanization of education and the process of education go back a long historical period. Eastern education has a unique approach to this issue, the interdependence of education and humanization of faith, the true essence of the Uzbek people, who embody not only national values, but also universal values. It is one of the urgent problems facing researchers and scientists conducting scientific research study of rich spiritual values in the field of education and upbringing, introduction of scientific and theoretical conclusions into pedagogical practice in terms of modern pedagogy and requirements of modern pedagogy. In this article, special attention was paid to the activity of the main topic humanization of didactic relations - the teacher. Because a teacher, as a specially trained person, should organize his work and the work of the student in a professional manner.

Conclusion: Didactic system is a critical system for humanizing teacher-student relationship. This system plays an important role in learning content, knowledge, and experience between teachers and students. A humanized didactic system strengthens the relationship between teachers and students and makes the learning process more effective. With this system, teachers are successful in teaching students knowledge, motivating them, and helping them to think independently and make decisions.

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